

1 **Influence of the imperfection direction on the ultimate response of steel frames**
2 **in advanced analysis**

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8 **ABSTRACT**

9 Initial geometric imperfections are unavoidable in steel members and frames due to erection and
10 manufacturing tolerances. These include frame out-of-plumbness, member out-of-straightness and cross-
11 sectional imperfections, and can have a significant influence on the response and resistance of steel
12 structures. Thus, they need to be accounted for in the analysis and design of steel structures, especially
13 when advanced design procedures are adopted. One of the easiest approaches to introduce geometric
14 imperfections in structural finite element models is through the linear superposition of scaled eigenmodes,
15 which are obtained from a priori elastic buckling analysis. Although the shape and magnitude of frame
16 and member imperfections are specified in international standards, the rules for the combination of
17 different types and directions of imperfections are unclear or impractical, and often require designers to
18 consider many possible combinations to find the critical, or “worst case”, shape of the imperfection
19 including the direction of each eigenmode. This paper investigates the influence of the direction of modes
20 contributing to the imperfection on the ultimate load (i.e., resistance) of steel frames when using advanced
21 analysis. Ultimate loads are estimated from advanced finite element simulations for 20 regular and
22 irregular unbraced frames featuring steel and austenitic stainless steel compact sections, in which initial
23 imperfections are modelled as linear superpositions of six scaled buckling modes considering all possible
24 combinations of direction. The results show that the influence of the imperfection direction on the ultimate
25 frame load is small, and that assuming a combination of all buckling modes with positive amplitudes
26 provides a simple and accurate estimation of the critical imperfection combination.

27 **KEYWORDS**

28 initial geometric imperfections, advanced analysis, elastic buckling analysis, steel frames, stainless steel
29 frames

30 **HIGHLIGHTS**

- 31 • Influence of the imperfection direction on the resistance of steel frames is investigated.
- 32 • Imperfections are modelled as a linear superposition of six scaled buckling modes.
- 33 • Different regular and irregular steel and stainless steel frames with compact sections are examined.
- 34 • Ultimate load factors for all possible direction combinations are obtained and compared.
- 35 • The notion of worst case imperfection is challenged.

36 **1. INTRODUCTION**

37 Initial geometric imperfections can have a significant influence on the resistance and stiffness of steel
38 frames, including frame out-of-plumbness imperfections, member out-of-straightness imperfections
39 and local cross-sectional imperfections. Traditionally, the effect of sway imperfections has been
40 accounted for in structural analyses by directly modelling the out-of-plumbness or through the use of
41 equivalent notional horizontal loads, while member and cross-section imperfections have been
42 implicitly considered in design expressions (e.g., the effect of member imperfections is incorporated in
43 member strength design curves, and local imperfections in local buckling expressions). However, with
44 the development and incorporation of direct design approaches in the current versions of international
45 standards such as AISC 360 [1], AISC 370 [2], prEN 1993-1-14 [3], AS/NZS 4100 [4] and
46 AS/NZS 4600 [5], a different and more detailed definition of initial geometric imperfections is required.
47 In these direct design approaches, the resistance of the structure is directly evaluated from the analysis
48 without requiring further resistance checks, and thus the incorporation of appropriate initial
49 imperfections in the developed advanced finite element (FE) models is critical.

50 The most common approaches to consider the effects of initial geometric imperfections in advanced
51 analysis are the modelling of imperfections by directly offsetting the coordinates of the nodes, the
52 reduction of member stiffness, the adoption of notional horizontal forces and the superposition of scaled
53 elastic buckling modes [6]. While the first approach is not practical for everyday engineering practice,
54 one of the advantages of the stiffness reduction method is that it does not require an explicit modelling
55 of the imperfections. Although several stiffness-reduction factors have been proposed to account for the
56 effect of initial geometric imperfections [7-9], they have not been assessed through probabilistic

57 approaches. The notional horizontal force method has been widely adopted in different structural
58 standards [1-5,10] for its simplicity, since it allows modelling structures in their theoretically perfect
59 configuration and taking into account the effect of frame and member imperfections by introducing a
60 set of equivalent horizontal forces. Typically, the elastic buckling mode approach assumes that the first
61 eigenmode represents the most critical imperfection and it is scaled and introduced as the initial
62 imperfection of the structure [10]. However, the actual failure mode of the structure may be different
63 from the first buckling mode due to the significant plastic deformations and load redistribution
64 occurring in advanced analysis. In this case, failure may occur in parts of the structure deficiently
65 represented in the first buckling mode and hence, to ensure imperfections are introduced in all members,
66 it is recommendable to include additional higher order eigenmodes when incorporating initial geometric
67 imperfections [11]. Although the amplitude and the shape or pattern of each initial imperfection type
68 are prescribed in specifications, and the different alternatives discussed above exist to input the
69 imperfections in finite element models, standards usually require that the most critical combination of
70 imperfection directions resulting in the minimum resistance be adopted as the nominal resistance of the
71 structure. This is generally not practical, since the number of possible imperfection combinations is
72 significant even for relatively simple frames. Furthermore, it can be argued that the treatment of initial
73 imperfections may be different in the context of the traditional two-step design methods and for system-
74 based direct design approaches.

75 In the traditional two-step design methodology, the prevailing analysis type for determining internal
76 actions is the geometric nonlinear analysis (GNA), which elastically amplifies deformations caused by
77 applied loads and frame out-of-plumbness imperfections, while member out-of-straightness
78 imperfections and local cross-sectional imperfections are not modelled. In rigid and semi-rigid
79 construction, moments are transferred through connections whereby vertical and inclined members are
80 invariably subjected to both compression and bending, and hence need to be designed for combined
81 loading. This is typically done using interaction equations, the simplest form of which is linear (Eq. 1),
82 and which are generally conservative.

$$\frac{N_{GNA}}{\phi_c N_m} + \frac{M_{GNA}}{\phi_b M_m} = 1 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

83 where (N_{GNA}, M_{GNA}) are the internal actions predicted by GNA analysis and (N_m, M_m) and (ϕ_c, ϕ_b)
 84 are the nominal member resistances and the resistance factors for compression and bending,
 85 respectively. In the Eurocode terminology, the interaction equation becomes Eq. 2, in which
 86 $(N_{b,Rk}, M_{b,Rk})$ are the characteristic member resistances for compression and bending and γ_{M1} is the
 87 partial safety factor for instability.

$$\frac{N_{GNA}}{N_{b,Rk}/\gamma_{M1}} + \frac{M_{GNA}}{M_{b,Rk}/\gamma_{M1}} = 1 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

88
 89 The member capacities (N_m, M_m) or $(N_{b,Rk}, M_{b,Rk})$ are calculated using strength curves derived from
 90 tests and advanced numerical analyses based on a target value of member out-of-straightness, e.g.,
 91 $L/1000$, where L is the member length. The ultimate capacity of the frame is deemed to be reached when
 92 the first (critical) member reaches its capacity, i.e., Eq. 1 or Eq. 2 are satisfied. The strength curves for
 93 calculating the member resistances are typically chosen to produce the mean or characteristic value of
 94 resistance when averaged over a length range, the reference being the target out-of-straightness chosen
 95 for the tests and advanced analysis. The resistance factors and the partial safety factor are calibrated such
 96 that the probability of the internal actions exceeding their respective member design capacity (e.g., N_{GNA}
 97 $> \phi_c N_m$) does not exceed a target value, typically expressed as a target reliability index (β_m). The
 98 calculation of these factors depends on the bias and variance of the strength curves relative to the “true”
 99 experimental and numerical resistances, which refer to the reference value of out-of-straightness.

100 In this procedure, it is implicitly assumed that the actual out-of-straightness imperfection of the
 101 critical member first reaching its capacity equals the target value, typically the tolerance value. The
 102 probability that this is the case is small as the imperfection of structural members very rarely reaches
 103 the tolerance value. A statistically more consistent approach would be to use the mean value of out-of-
 104 straightness, e.g., $L/1490$ as reported by Bjorhovde [12], or an updated mean value based on more
 105 recent data, e.g., $L/1996$ [13], since the mean value represents the most likely value of imperfection of
 106 any member, including the critical. The variance of the actual value of out-of-straightness of the critical
 107 member relative to the mean value is accounted for by considering the coefficient of variation of the
 108 design value relative to the test or “true” resistance in the reliability calibration.

109 It is evident that if higher strength curves based on a smaller target value of out-of-straightness are
110 used for determining member resistances, and assuming the resistance of real specimens featuring
111 random imperfection amplitudes represents the “true” resistance of the members, the resistance factors
112 (ϕ_c, ϕ_b) would reduce if the target reliability index (β_m) is unchanged because the resistance reserve
113 due to the conservatism of the strength curve would reduce. On the contrary, the partial safety factors
114 (γ_{M1}) would increase under the same circumstances. Alternatively, if the resistance or partial safety
115 factors are unchanged, the reliability index would reduce. These relationships emphasise the intrinsic
116 interdependency between the chosen target out-of-straightness and the calculated reliability index.

117 Summarising this discussion of the traditional two-step design methodology,

- 118 1. the structure is assumed to fail when the first (critical) member reaches its capacity,
- 119 2. it is implicitly assumed that the out-of-straightness of the critical member equals the target value,
- 120 3. the target value of out-of-straightness is usually chosen as a tolerance value, whereas a
121 statistically sound approach would be to choose the mean value of out-of-straightness,
- 122 4. the amplification of moments is underestimated when GNA analysis is used to calculate internal
123 actions, and
- 124 5. the resistance of members subject to combined compression and bending is calculated using
125 interaction curves which are typically conservative.

126 The calculation of resistance and partial safety factors to a target reliability index (β_m) is subject to
127 these assumptions and inaccuracies.

128 The system-based direct design approaches are considerably more statistically consistent in their
129 calculation of system resistance and partial safety factors [14,15]. The calibration uses accurate
130 statistical functions obtained from field measurements (e.g., [11,16-18]) to represent all main random
131 variables including out-of-straightness [17-20]. Monte-Carlo type simulations are performed
132 considering the variance of all random variables in computing the probability of failure, which may be
133 expressed in terms of the system reliability index (β_s), and the system resistance factor (ϕ_s) or the
134 system partial safety factor ($\gamma_{M,s}$) are chosen so that the system reliability index meets or exceeds the
135 target value. The direct design allows additional loading past the failure of the first critical members

136 when load redistribution is possible until the complete failure of the frame. In this framework, the shape
137 of the imperfection is chosen to produce resistances statistically consistent with the resistance of frames
138 with measured shapes of imperfection [11]. In particular, the mean value of amplitude of out-of-
139 straightness is the mean measured value, typically less than the tolerance value.

140 Direct design approaches require a nominal model be specified, including nominal values of material
141 properties, geometric imperfections, residual stresses, etc. The choice of nominal geometric
142 imperfection is largely arbitrary as the influence of the particular choice of nominal imperfection is
143 reflected in the reliability calibration which produces the system ϕ_s or $\gamma_{M,S}$ factors. It is possible, in the
144 framework of system-based direct design, to adopt the more restrictive approach of determining the
145 nominal resistance as the minimum resistance, which allows specifying less conservative values of ϕ_s
146 and $\gamma_{M,S}$. Or conversely, it is also possible to accept a more permissive combination of initial
147 imperfections and to prescribe the associated more conservative system factors.

148 Because system resistance and ϕ_s , $\gamma_{M,S}$ -factors are now being calibrated for inclusion in
149 international standards for the first time, it is timely for national standardisation committees to decide
150 how initial imperfections should be treated in the determination of system nominal resistances and to
151 prescribe system factors accordingly. In this consideration, it follows from the above discussion that
152 the reliability indices obtained from the traditional two-step design methodology and system-based
153 direct design approaches are not directly comparable. Seeing that the two-step design methodology
154 ignores the potential additional capacity of the frame achievable by load redistribution in statically
155 redundant frames after the critical member reaches its capacity, the system target reliability index should
156 be chosen to be at least that of members for the two-step design methodology. Equally, if the frame is
157 statically determinate, or failure occurs in a statically determinate part of a redundant frame, no load
158 redistribution is possible and the target reliability of the two approaches should be equal,
159 notwithstanding the inaccuracies associated with the member-based approach summarised above.

160 With the aim of simplifying the definition of initial imperfections in design, this paper investigates
161 the influence of the direction of initial imperfections modelled as linear superpositions of buckling
162 modes on the resistance of steel and stainless steel frames designed using advanced analysis. Section 2

163 provides an overview of the methodologies adopted in current structural standards for modelling initial
164 imperfections and presents the alternative approach based on the superposition of buckling modes
165 proposed in [11]. In Section 3, the benchmark frames used in the assessment are presented and the
166 developed advanced finite element models are described. Finally, Section 4 presents the analysis of the
167 variability in the resistances for different combinations of imperfection directions, and proposes a
168 simple approach to modelling geometric imperfections without performing multiple analyses.

169 **2. MODELLING OF INITIAL GEOMETRIC IMPERFECTIONS**

170 2.1. INITIAL GEOMETRIC IMPERFECTIONS IN STANDARDS

171 Most major international design standards for steel structures prescribe design values for the different
172 types of imperfections and specify how to include them in structural analyses, being rather consistent
173 among the different standards. The definition of nominal initial geometric imperfections differs
174 depending on the considered design method: in general, the consideration of frame out-of-plumbness
175 (sway) imperfections is always required, while member imperfections only need to be included when
176 advanced analyses are carried out.

177 The AISC 360 [1] and AISC 370 [2] Specifications require that out-of-plumbness imperfections
178 corresponding to a nominal initial storey out-of-plumb angle ϕ of 1/500 be included when the Direct
179 Analysis Method is adopted by directly modifying the position of the nodes or through the use of notional
180 loads, although the explicit modelling of initial out-of-straightness of individual members is not
181 necessary since these imperfections are accounted for in the design provisions for compression
182 members. Conversely, the analysis shall include the effects of system imperfections (with amplitudes
183 of $\phi = 1/500$) and member imperfections (with amplitudes of $L/1000$) when the advanced analysis
184 provisions given in Appendix 1 are adopted, and the use of notional loads to represent either type of
185 imperfection is not permitted. Since advanced analysis provisions in [1,2] are currently limited to
186 compact sections, it is not necessary to include cross-sectional imperfections in the FE model.

187 Regarding global sway imperfections, prEN 1993-1-14 [3] refers to prEN 1993-1-1 [10], which
188 prescribes a basic out-of-plumb angle of $\phi_0 = 1/400$ when cross-sections and members are checked
189 elastically, or $\phi_0 = 1/200$ for when cross-sections and members are verified using plastic resistances,
190 and may be replaced by systems of equivalent horizontal forces, or the assumed shape derived from

191 elastic buckling analyses. For member imperfections, prEN 1993-1-14 [3] recommends an imperfection
192 amplitude of 80% of the geometric manufacturing tolerances given in EN 1090 [21], with a minimum
193 value of $L/1000$, and a half-sinusoidal shape along the member length. The use of equivalent
194 imperfections that account for the combined effect of geometric imperfections and residual stresses is
195 also permitted. The combination of imperfections should be chosen to identify the lowest resistance;
196 when the relevant directions are not evident, several imperfections with different directions should be
197 investigated. Finally, cross-sectional imperfections should also be included when designing plated and
198 cold-formed structures using advanced analysis.

199 The AS 4100 [4] and AS/NZS 4600 [5] Specifications for steel and cold-formed steel structures
200 require that only the effect of frame imperfections with a basic out-of-plumb angle value of $\phi_0 = 1/200$
201 be accounted for, as the effect of cross-sectional and member imperfections are already included in the
202 elastic effective stiffnesses and member capacity calculations. However, when structures are designed
203 using advanced analysis, frame and member imperfections should be modelled, for which a reduced
204 out-of-plumb angle of $1/500$ and a maximum value of the member imperfection equal to $L/1000$ are
205 prescribed. While the advanced analysis approach is limited to compact sections in the AS 4100 [4]
206 Specification for steel structures, and thus the modelling of cross-sectional imperfections is not
207 necessary, the AS/NZS 4600 [5] Specification for cold-formed steel structures requires that local and
208 distortional imperfections be included in the analysis, with the modes determined from linear buckling
209 analyses and the scaling amplitudes given in [5]. Nevertheless, the incorporation of local and
210 distortional imperfections is not required in advanced analysis of unbraced frames or racks.

211 In summary, the amplitudes assumed in the different specifications for initial out-of-plumb
212 imperfections range between $1/500$ and $1/200$, while for member imperfections a consistent value of
213 $L/1000$ is prescribed. These values are, however, significantly higher than the initial geometric
214 imperfections measured from actual structures and reported in the literature. The measurements carried
215 out on a series of multi-storey buildings [22,23] suggested that frame imperfections exhibit a mean
216 value of 0.0013 and a standard deviation of 0.00114, which correspond to out-of-plumb angles of $1/770$
217 and $1/877$, respectively [11]. Likewise, member imperfection amplitudes reported in the literature also

218 tend to be remarkably lower than the nominal $L/1000$ value prescribed in the codes, with mean values
219 of $L/1996$ reported for hot-rolled steel I-section members [13] and $L/3232$ for cold-formed stainless
220 steel rectangular hollow section columns [16], for example.

221 2.2. INITIAL GEOMETRIC IMPERFECTIONS AS SUPERPOSITION OF BUCKLING MODES

222 The approaches for modelling initial geometric imperfections currently prescribed in international
223 specifications are overconservative and present some additional problems, including the difficulties
224 associated with the offset of the node coordinates when the design software does not include specific
225 tools for the direct definition of imperfections, or the identification of the most critical combination of
226 imperfection directions. With the aim of simplifying the definition and input of initial geometric
227 imperfections for advanced analysis, a new procedure in which initial geometric imperfections are
228 defined as a linear superposition of numerous buckling modes and a suitable amplitude is assigned to
229 each of these modes was proposed by Shayan et al. [11]. Defining initial imperfections based not only
230 on the first buckling mode, but as a combination of numerous eigenmodes, ensures that imperfections
231 are induced in virtually all members, thereby triggering the instability associated to the actual failure
232 mode of the structure [11,24].

233 The study presented in [11] concluded that the first six modes are sufficient to accurately represent
234 the actual shape of the initial imperfections in steel frames, and suitable imperfection amplitudes were
235 proposed for each of the six modes. According to [11], the amplitude A_j corresponding to the buckling
236 mode j can be determined from Eq. 3, where P_j is the normalized scale (participation) factor, F is the
237 amplitude factor ($F = 0.003$ when six buckling modes are adopted), and H and L correspond to the
238 total frame height and member length, respectively.

$$A_j = \begin{cases} P_j \cdot F \cdot H & \text{for sway modes} \\ P_j \cdot F \cdot L & \text{for non – sway modes} \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

239 The normalized participation factors P_j were calibrated based on statistical data for initial geometric
240 imperfections obtained from the literature, considering a range of regular and irregular low-to-mid-rise
241 frames under gravity loads, and the values summarized in Table 1 were recommended for braced and
242 unbraced frames. While the scale factors calibrated for the different buckling modes in braced frames
243

244 were very similar since all modes represented member out-of-straightness imperfections (see the P_j
245 values in Table 1), the scale factor calibrated for the first mode in unbraced frames – which represents
246 the out-of-plumbness of the frame – was significantly higher than those corresponding to higher modes.
247 Since the imperfection amplitudes A_j were calibrated for a wide range of frames based on statistical
248 data representing actual steel structures, the derived scale factors were deemed to be applicable to
249 typical frames and have been adopted in this study to evaluate the influence of the imperfection direction
250 on the resistance of steel frames.

251 3. BENCHMARK FRAMES

252 3.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE FRAMES

253 The effect of the imperfection direction on the frame resistance has been assessed for a set of different
254 frame layouts and different materials similar to those adopted in [11,25,26]. The database comprises
255 simple frames (see Figure 1), the multi-storey and multi-bay frames shown in Figure 2 and the irregular
256 frames presented in Figure 3, which were subjected to vertical point loads or uniformly distributed
257 loads, including a broad range of frame geometries and boundary conditions. For each of the 20 layouts,
258 structural steel and austenitic stainless steel materials were considered to assess whether the nonlinear
259 stress-strain behaviour exhibited by stainless steel alloys had any influence on the effect of the
260 imperfection direction.

261 The constitutive model for structural steel was assumed elastic-perfectly plastic, while to describe the
262 nonlinear stress-strain relationship of the austenitic stainless steel alloy the two-stage Ramberg-Osgood
263 model proposed in [27] was adopted. The material properties assumed for the structural steel and
264 austenitic stainless steel frames are summarized in Table 2, in which E is the Young's modulus, f_y is
265 the yield stress, f_u is the ultimate tensile strength, ε_u is the ultimate tensile strain and n and m are the
266 nonlinear exponents for the two-stage Ramberg-Osgood model. All frames comprised compact I-
267 section beams and columns with uniform member sizes, which were chosen from the European HEB
268 series to produce member slenderness values of $\bar{\lambda}_c = 1.0$. The member slenderness was calculated from
269 $\bar{\lambda}_c = \sqrt{N_{pl}/N_{cr}}$, where N_{pl} is the squash load of the cross-section and N_{cr} is the elastic buckling load.
270 For $\bar{\lambda}_c = 1.0$, the elastic buckling load and the squash load coincide, and structures show the greatest

271 sensitivity to initial imperfection around this slenderness value [11,28,29]. In addition, the database was
272 extended to include additional 20 frames with HEB 340 cross-section beams and columns for the
273 structural steel material, which resulted in member slenderness values ranging between $\bar{\lambda}_c = 0.3 - 2.4$.
274 In total, 60 different frames were investigated.

275 3.2. FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

276 Steel and stainless steel frames were modelled using the general-purpose finite element software
277 ABAQUS [30] and using the 2-noded linear B310S beam element available in the library, which is
278 capable of accounting for the spread of plasticity through the cross-section and along the member
279 length. Frames were restrained in the out-of-plane direction so that only in-plane major axis
280 bending/buckling was considered. The ultimate load factors for each frame, which are the load factors
281 corresponding to the ultimate load or resistance of the frames, were determined from second-order
282 inelastic analyses that accounted for all material and geometric nonlinearities (advanced analysis) using
283 the Riks arc-length technique available in ABAQUS [30].

284 Beam-to-column connections were assumed to be rigid, and loads were introduced in the beams or
285 at the beam-to-column joints using distributed or point loads, as indicated in Figures 1-3. The base
286 supports of most of the frames were assumed as fixed, although frames with pin-ended boundary
287 conditions were also investigated (i.e., Frames 2 and 15). Material properties were introduced as user-
288 defined true stress-plastic strain relationships using the elastic-perfectly plastic or nonlinear [27]
289 material models for structural steel and stainless steel, respectively. In order to investigate the influence
290 of imperfection direction only on the ultimate frame resistances, residual stresses were not taken into
291 account in this study, following the approach adopted in [11].

292 Initial geometric imperfections were introduced as a superposition of the first six buckling modes
293 using the *IMPERFECTION option in ABAQUS, which were obtained from a priori elastic buckling
294 analysis, and the amplitudes of each mode were determined from the scaling factors proposed in [11]
295 and described in Section 2.2. All possible combinations of imperfection directions were investigated by
296 assigning a positive (+1) or negative (-1) sign to each of these amplitudes and by combining them using
297 the MESH combination option available in ABAQUS [30], which resulted in $2^6 = 64$ different
298 analyses for each of the investigated frames. The MESH combination pattern in ABAQUS combines

299 every sampled value of a parameter with every sampled value of every other parameter in the parametric
300 study [30]; considering that the sampled parameters in this study were the signs of the six imperfection
301 shapes determined from the elastic buckling analyses (parameters adopted the values [-1,+1]), this
302 procedure guaranteed that the two possible directions (i.e, signs) of each mode were combined with all
303 the possible directions of the other five imperfection shapes. In total, 3840 advanced analyses were
304 performed on steel and stainless steel frames. Figure 4 shows three examples of imperfection direction
305 combinations for Frame 1: the initial imperfection pattern corresponding to the linear superposition of
306 six buckling modes with all positive (red) and all negative (blue) amplitudes are shown, in addition to
307 an intermediate case with a combination of positive and negative directions (green). The initial
308 geometry of the perfect frame is also shown as reference.

309 **4. INFLUENCE OF THE IMPERFECTION DIRECTION ON THE FRAME RESISTANCE**

310 4.1. ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE

311 To illustrate the influence of the initial imperfection introduced in finite element models, a simple
312 pitched portal frame subjected to two point loads at the beam-to-column joints (see Frame 6 in Figure
313 1) was investigated. Several advanced analyses with different initial geometric imperfections were
314 carried out, and the failure modes and frame resistances were compared. Imperfection patterns including
315 global sway imperfections and member imperfections were obtained from an elastic buckling analysis,
316 and combined using different amplitudes. Figure 5 shows the failure modes and ultimate loads (taken
317 as the maximum loads of the load-displacement curves and which represent the resistance of the frames)
318 obtained for Frame 6 considering different types, combinations and amplitudes of sway and member
319 imperfections. When combinations of sway and member imperfections were considered following the
320 requirements in international steel standards, using amplitudes of $\phi = 1/200$ and $e_0 = L/1000$,
321 respectively, the advanced simulations predicted sway-type failure modes and the same ultimate loads
322 for the four possible combinations of frame and member imperfection directions (see Figure 5(a)),
323 which indicated a negligible effect of the imperfection directions on the ultimate response of the frame.

324 On the contrary, when only member imperfections following the non-sway buckling modes and
325 amplitudes e_0 of the member imperfection equal to $L/1000$ and $L/200$ were introduced, a clear
326 dependency on the imperfection direction was observed for the two amplitudes of member imperfection.

327 The failure modes and ultimate loads reported in Figure 5(c)-(f) highlight the influence and importance
328 of the initial imperfection pattern considered in advanced analysis, as the choice of some imperfection
329 combinations led to failure modes similar to those obtained when global sway imperfections were
330 introduced (cases (c) and (f), when the imperfections of both columns lean in the same direction), while
331 other combinations resulted in significantly higher ultimate load predictions when they locked in failure
332 modes with higher critical loads (as per cases (d) and (e)). The values of the ultimate loads were different
333 for the two member imperfection amplitudes considered (i.e., $L/1000$ and $L/200$), as shown in Figure
334 5, but the conclusions are the same. The analysis also showed that even for very small initial sway
335 imperfection amplitudes (i.e., $\phi = 1/5000$, significantly smaller than the $1/200$ or $1/500$ values
336 specified in the codes), the frame exhibited sway-type failure modes for the four combinations of
337 member imperfection directions (as per in Figure 5(b)), although resulted in higher ultimate loads than
338 the $F_u = 282$ kN value predicted using the sway imperfection amplitude prescribed in the codes (case
339 (a)). This highlighted the influence out-of-plumbness imperfections had not only on the ultimate load
340 of the frame, but also on the failure mode observed. In a similar way, the fact that small sway
341 imperfections were sufficient to result in sway failure modes emphasizes the importance of introducing
342 a combination of different buckling modes as initial imperfections when designing frames using
343 advanced analysis (especially sway imperfections), to ensure that the critical shape is present and that
344 the instability associated with the actual failure mode of the structure is triggered [11,24].

345 4.2. INFLUENCE OF THE INITIAL IMPERFECTION DIRECTION

346 The influence of the imperfection direction on the frame resistance is assessed in this Section based on
347 the finite element analyses of steel and stainless steel frames presented in Section 3. Advanced finite
348 element analyses (i.e., GMNIA analyses) were carried out for each of the frame layouts, cross-sections
349 and materials investigated, in which initial geometric imperfections were introduced as the linear
350 superposition of the first six buckling modes using the amplitudes recommended in [11] and introduced
351 in Section 2.2. The study considered all possible combinations of imperfection directions for the six
352 buckling modes, obtaining 64 different ultimate load factors λ_u for each frame investigated, and the
353 variability of these load factors was evaluated.

354 The assessment of the ultimate load factors λ_u is presented in Tables 3-5. While Table 3 presents the
355 results for steel frames with multiple column slenderness $\bar{\lambda}_c$ values (constant HEB 340 cross-section
356 assumed for all columns and beams), Tables 4 and 5 report the results for steel and stainless steel frames
357 with column slenderness values of $\bar{\lambda}_c = 1.0$, respectively. In these tables, the maximum-to-minimum
358 ultimate load factor ratios $\lambda_{u,max}/\lambda_{u,min}$ and the coefficients of variation (COV) of the ultimate load
359 factors are reported for each frame considered. The $\lambda_{u,max}$ load factor corresponds to the maximum of
360 the 64 ultimate load factor values predicted for each frame, while $\lambda_{u,min}$ is the minimum of the 64
361 ultimate load factor values, which according to the draft European guidelines [3] corresponds to the
362 most critical combination of initial imperfections and should be adopted as the nominal imperfection
363 when designing with advanced analysis. Tables 3-5 also report the $\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$ ratios, where $\lambda_{u,pos}$
364 is the ultimate load factor for the imperfection combination that assumes all positive amplitudes, and
365 the percentage of ultimate load factors below $\lambda_{u,pos}$ for each frame. Note that when determining the
366 imperfection shape assuming all positive amplitudes, the mode shapes are taken as produced by the
367 buckling analysis, and so are arbitrarily assigned a sign, i.e., the direction of the individual buckling
368 mode is arbitrary.

369 The results shown in Tables 3-5 suggest that the influence of the imperfection direction on the
370 predicted ultimate frame load is small. The differences between the maximum and minimum load
371 factors within each frame lie between 0 and 6%, and very low coefficients of variation are observed
372 (0.00-0.03). Given that the normalized scale factors P_i reported in Table 1 for buckling modes 2 to 6
373 representing the out-of-straightness of members are significantly lower than the P_1 factor for the out-
374 of-plumbness of unbraced frames, these results suggest that the influence of the highest buckling modes
375 on the ultimate load of the investigated frames is low. This is in line with the sensitivity analysis results
376 reported in [28], which indicated that the influence of the initial sway imperfections on the resistance
377 of steel frames is much more significant than that of initial member imperfections. The results also
378 show that the variability in the ultimate load factors is not significantly affected by the material or the
379 type of frame, since the $\lambda_{u,max}/\lambda_{u,min}$ ratios and COV values reported in Tables 3-5 are very similar
380 for steel and stainless steel frames, and for simple, multi-storey, multi-bay and irregular frames.

381 The $\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$ ratios reported in these tables also indicate that while, in general, the ultimate
382 load factors corresponding to the critical imperfection combination $\lambda_{u,min}$ of course are lower than the
383 ultimate load factors for the imperfection combination with all positive amplitudes $\lambda_{u,pos}$, the
384 differences observed are insignificant, with all $\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$ ratios ranging between 1.00-1.01 in
385 Tables 3-5. The number of imperfection direction combination cases in which the ultimate load factor
386 is lower than $\lambda_{u,pos}$ depends on the frame, but ranges between 0-58%. The same results are illustrated
387 in Figure 6, in which the $\lambda_{u,max}/\lambda_{u,min}$ and $\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$ ratios are presented for the different steel
388 and stainless steel frames investigated as functions of the member slenderness of the critical column $\bar{\lambda}_c$.
389 These results indicate that the maximum variability in ultimate load factors (i.e., highest $\lambda_{u,max}/\lambda_{u,min}$
390 ratios) generally occurs for frames with member slenderness values $\bar{\lambda}_c$ of around 1.0, while the influence
391 of $\bar{\lambda}_c$ on the $\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$ ratios is less remarkable.

392 Overall, the assessment of the ultimate load factors presented in this Section highlights the fact that
393 the adoption of a linear combination of buckling modes that assumes all modes with positive amplitudes
394 ($\lambda_{u,pos}$) is a simple approach that estimates the minimum ultimate load ($\lambda_{u,min}$) with good accuracy,
395 without requiring that all possible combinations be considered to find the critical imperfection
396 combination, as required by prEN 1993-1-14 [3]. Provided sufficient imperfection types are introduced
397 through the consideration of different sway and non-sway modes, designers can simply adopt initial
398 geometric imperfections resulting from the approach proposed in [11], with all positive amplitudes, and
399 obtain a sufficiently accurate prediction of the ultimate frame load. Figure 7 shows the histogram for all
400 the ultimate load factors λ_u normalized by the corresponding $\lambda_{u,pos}$ factor for all the frames considered
401 in the analysis. Figure 7 clearly shows that the great majority of the $\lambda_u/\lambda_{u,pos}$ ratios lie in the 0.99-1.02
402 range, with the mean and standard deviation of $\lambda_u/\lambda_{u,pos}$ being 1.009 and 0.014, respectively.

403 It should be noted that the total imperfection amplitudes resulting from the mode scale factors
404 proposed in [11] are sometimes significantly lower than those prescribed in the different specifications,
405 as discussed in Section 2.1. To evaluate the actual imperfection amplitudes introduced in the finite
406 element models by means of the linear superposition of the six buckling modes, sway and member
407 imperfections were back-calculated from the developed ABAQUS models using the initial node

408 coordinates. Out-of-plumb angles were estimated from the relative displacements of the bottom and top
409 ends of the columns, while member imperfections were calculated as the differences between the total
410 imperfections and the imperfections corresponding to the out-of-plumbness for each node. From these
411 results, out-of-plumb angles determined from the participation and amplitude factors reported in Table
412 1 were found to lie between $1/260$ and $1/1080$ for the frames analysed, while the resulting member
413 imperfection amplitudes ranged between $L/825$ and $L/8440$, depending on the column considered. In
414 order to evaluate whether the conclusions drawn in this Section are still valid for frames with larger
415 initial imperfections, similar to those prescribed in the codes, the influence of the imperfection
416 amplitude on the variability of ultimate load factors is investigated in the next Section.

417 4.3. INFLUENCE OF THE INITIAL IMPERFECTION AMPLITUDE

418 As indicated above, the imperfection amplitudes resulting from the combination of the different
419 buckling modes using the scaling parameters proposed in [11] are considerably lower than the values
420 typically prescribed in design provisions for sway and member imperfections for some of the
421 investigated frames, since the amplitude factor F was calibrated using data on actual initial imperfection
422 measurements. With the objective of assessing the influence of the initial imperfection amplitude on
423 the variability of the frame resistance, and whether the conclusions drawn in Section 4.2 are still valid
424 for higher imperfection amplitudes, more similar to those specified in the codes, the analysis presented
425 in the previous Section was repeated for four of the frames investigated (Frame 1, Frame 12, Frame 17
426 and Frame 20) assuming imperfection amplitudes equal to two times the values proposed in [11] (i.e.,
427 adopting $F = 0.006$ in Eq. 3). The imperfections resulting from this assumption lie between out-of-
428 plumb angles of $1/130$ and $1/540$ and member imperfection amplitudes between $L/413$ and $L/4220$,
429 and thus constitute an upper limit to the initial imperfection magnitudes prescribed in the codes.

430 Results were obtained for steel frames with member slenderness values of $\bar{\lambda}_c = 1.0$, since the
431 analysis presented in Section 4.2 showed that while there is very little influence of the material type,
432 the maximum deviations in ultimate load factors occur for $\bar{\lambda}_c = 1.0$. The $\lambda_{u,max}/\lambda_{u,min}$ and
433 $\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$ ratios corresponding to the new analysis are reported in Table 6, where the coefficients
434 of variation of the ultimate load factors and the cases with $\lambda_u < \lambda_{u,pos}$ are also included. Comparing

435 the results in Table 6 with the equivalent values reported in Table 4, it can be seen that the
436 $\lambda_{u,max}/\lambda_{u,min}$ ratios and COV values increase for higher imperfection amplitudes, as does the number
437 of cases with ultimate load factors below $\lambda_{u,pos}$. However, the $\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$ ratios remain practically
438 unchanged. This indicates that although the variability of the load factors is slightly higher, the adoption
439 of initial geometric imperfections resulting from the superposition of buckling modes with all positive
440 directions is still acceptable for imperfection amplitudes similar to those prescribed in the different
441 specifications. As the $\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$ ratios observed for $F = 0.003$ and $F = 0.006$ were similar, it is inferred
442 that the results for the amplitudes prescribed in specifications will lie within the two scenarios investigated.

443 Finally, Figure 8 compares the ultimate load factors obtained for the original amplitude factor $F =$
444 0.003 proposed in [11] with those corresponding to the double imperfection amplitudes investigated in
445 this Section for the four frames analysed. The ratios between the ultimate load factors λ_u corresponding
446 to $F = 0.006$ and $F = 0.003$ (i.e., $\lambda_{u,F=0.006}/\lambda_{u,F=0.003}$) were calculated for the same imperfection
447 direction combinations, and plotted for Frame 1, Frame 12, Frame 17 and Frame 20 to evaluate the
448 influence of the initial imperfection amplitudes on the frame resistance. The ratios reported in Figure 8
449 indicated that, as expected, the $\lambda_{u,F=0.006}/\lambda_{u,F=0.003}$ ratios lie below unity for all the frames
450 investigated in this Section because the ultimate load factors corresponding to the larger imperfection
451 amplitudes $\lambda_{u,F=0.006}$ were lower. Figure 8 also shows that the different frames exhibited a distinct
452 sensitivity to the initial imperfection magnitude, with Frame 12 being the most sensitive among the frames
453 analysed, with a difference in ultimate loads of around 10%, followed by Frame 1, with a 5% difference,
454 and Frames 20 and 17, with differences of 3% and 1%, respectively. The results also showed that the
455 influence of the initial imperfection amplitude on the ultimate loads was quite uniform for the different
456 imperfection direction combinations, which ultimately results in similar levels of ultimate load factor
457 variability for the two imperfection amplitude levels, $F = 0.003$ and $F = 0.006$, as discussed above.

458 5. CONCLUSIONS

459 Initial imperfections present in steel structures include global (frame) sway imperfections, member out-
460 of-straightness imperfections and cross-sectional (local or distortional) imperfections. The nonlinear
461 response of structures can be considerably influenced by initial geometric imperfections, and both the

462 stiffness and the resistance can be affected. Hence, initial imperfections need to be modelled in
463 advanced structural finite element models. Based on the method proposed by Shayan et al. [11] to model
464 initial geometric imperfections as a linear combination of the first six buckling modes, this paper
465 investigates the influence of the imperfection direction on the ultimate response of steel and stainless
466 steel frames in advanced analysis. The study is based on a set of simple, multi-storey, multi-bay and
467 irregular unbraced frames, featuring structural steel and austenitic stainless steel alloys and a range of
468 member slenderness values, for which the ultimate load factors corresponding to all the different
469 possible combinations of imperfection directions were determined and analysed. The assessment of the
470 ultimate load factors showed that the influence of the imperfection direction on the ultimate load is
471 small for the investigated frames, and no significant differences were observed for simple, multi-storey,
472 multi-bay or irregular frames or for different materials. The results also indicated that the adoption of a
473 linear combination of buckling modes that assumes all six modes with positive amplitudes is a simple
474 yet congruous approach to modelling geometric imperfections. For codes that require the geometric
475 imperfection to be chosen as the worst case scenario, the approach provides resistances close to the
476 minimum frame resistance.

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TABLES

Table 1. Recommended participation factors and amplitude factors to model initial geometric imperfections in steel frames using six buckling modes [11].

Type of frame	P_1	P_2	P_3	P_4	P_5	P_6	F
Braced frames	0.20	0.20	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.003
Unbraced frames	0.40	0.10	0.15	0.15	0.10	0.10	0.003

Table 2. Material properties for structural steel and austenitic stainless steel frames.

Alloy	E [MPa]	f_y [MPa]	f_u [MPa]	ε_u [mm/mm]	n [-]	m [-]
Structural steel	210,000	235	-	-	-	-
Austenitic stainless steel	200,000	310	670	0.54	6.3	2.6

Table 3. Ultimate load factor assessment for steel frames with HEB 340 cross-section (multiple column slenderness $\bar{\lambda}_c$ values).

Frame	$\lambda_{u,max}/\lambda_{u,min}$	COV	$\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$	Cases below $\lambda_{u,pos}$ [%]
Frame 1	1.040	0.013	1.000	0.0
Frame 2	1.027	0.012	1.002	37.5
Frame 3	1.003	0.000	1.003	6.3
Frame 4	1.002	0.001	1.002	31.3
Frame 5	1.039	0.010	1.010	1.6
Frame 6	1.029	0.011	1.000	0.0
Frame 7	1.025	0.011	1.004	25.0
Frame 8	1.045	0.015	1.003	9.4
Frame 9	1.032	0.015	1.000	0.0
Frame 10	1.029	0.014	1.000	0.0
Frame 11	1.009	0.002	1.009	3.1
Frame 12	1.020	0.007	1.000	0.0
Frame 13	1.005	0.002	1.002	48.4
Frame 14	1.026	0.010	1.004	25.0
Frame 15	1.033	0.016	1.002	37.5
Frame 16	1.023	0.008	1.006	32.8
Frame 17	1.024	0.011	1.002	31.3
Frame 18	1.051	0.025	1.000	0.0
Frame 19	1.001	0.000	1.001	3.1
Frame 20	1.008	0.004	1.008	50.0

Table 4. Ultimate load factor assessment for steel frames with column slenderness $\bar{\lambda}_c = 1.0$.

Frame	$\lambda_{u,max}/\lambda_{u,min}$	COV	$\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$	Cases below $\lambda_{u,pos}$ [%]
Frame 1	1.041	0.014	1.001	1.6
Frame 2	1.036	0.014	1.006	26.6
Frame 3	1.002	0.001	1.002	57.8
Frame 4	1.010	0.005	1.000	0.0
Frame 5	1.040	0.013	1.004	9.4
Frame 6	1.038	0.013	1.000	0.0
Frame 7	1.031	0.011	1.004	26.6
Frame 8	1.037	0.015	1.004	15.6
Frame 9	1.035	0.013	1.000	0.0
Frame 10	1.030	0.015	1.000	0.0
Frame 11	1.010	0.003	1.010	12.5
Frame 12	1.015	0.007	1.001	1.6
Frame 13	1.010	0.005	1.000	0.0
Frame 14	1.024	0.011	1.003	25.0
Frame 15	1.040	0.019	1.000	0.0
Frame 16	1.026	0.008	1.006	31.3
Frame 17	1.012	0.005	1.001	3.1
Frame 18	1.055	0.026	1.000	0.0
Frame 19	1.003	0.000	1.002	9.4
Frame 20	1.020	0.004	1.010	15.6

Table 5. Ultimate load factor assessment for austenitic stainless steel frames with column slenderness $\bar{\lambda}_c = 1.0$.

Frame	$\lambda_{u,max}/\lambda_{u,min}$	COV	$\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$	Cases below $\lambda_{u,pos}$ [%]
Frame 1	1.032	0.013	1.000	0.0
Frame 2	1.033	0.011	1.002	21.9
Frame 3	1.003	0.001	1.001	12.5
Frame 4	1.011	0.005	1.001	4.7
Frame 5	1.030	0.011	1.010	10.9
Frame 6	1.030	0.011	1.000	0.0
Frame 7	1.051	0.024	1.000	0.0
Frame 8	1.032	0.015	1.002	21.9
Frame 9	1.022	0.010	1.000	0.0
Frame 10	1.030	0.015	1.000	0.0
Frame 11	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.0
Frame 12	1.012	0.006	1.001	21.9
Frame 13	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.0
Frame 14	1.030	0.008	1.010	7.8
Frame 15	1.034	0.015	1.002	25.0
Frame 16	1.012	0.005	1.001	14.1
Frame 17	1.023	0.011	1.000	0.0
Frame 18	1.060	0.025	1.000	0.0
Frame 19	1.023	0.009	1.000	0.0
Frame 20	1.001	0.001	1.001	34.4

Table 6. Ultimate load factor assessment for steel frames with column slenderness $\lambda_c = 1.0$ and double imperfection amplitude.

Frame	$\lambda_{u,max}/\lambda_{u,min}$	COV	$\lambda_{u,pos}/\lambda_{u,min}$	Cases below $\lambda_{u,pos}$ [%]
Frame 1	1.057	0.025	1.000	0.0
Frame 12	1.032	0.012	1.002	9.4
Frame 17	1.031	0.014	1.000	0.0
Frame 20	1.020	0.007	1.010	21.9

FIGURES

Figure 1. Simple frame layouts considered in the study (adapted from [25,26]).

Figure 2. Multi-storey and multi-bay frame layouts considered in the study (adapted from [25,26]).

Figure 2. Multi-storey and multi-bay frame layouts considered in the study (adapted from [25,26])
(*cont.*).

Figure 3. Irregular frame layouts considered in the study (adapted from [11]).

Figure 4. Initial geometric imperfection patterns resulting from the linear combination of six buckling modes with different directions (amplitude signs).

Figure 5. Illustrative example: failure modes and ultimate loads for Frame 6 considering different types, combinations and amplitudes of sway and member imperfections; imperfection shown in black insert in (c-f).

Figure 6. Assessment of the influence of the imperfection direction on the ultimate load factors λ_u for steel and stainless steel frames.

Figure 7. Histogram for the $\lambda_u / \lambda_{u,pos}$ ultimate load factor ratios for steel and stainless steel frames.

Figure 8. Influence of the initial imperfection amplitude on the frame resistance.